

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF QUALIMETRIC COMPETENCE IN PRESCHOOL STUDENTS

Kurbanova Mukhtasarkhan Bahromovna

Graduate student of Kokan University

Abstract. In this article, detailed comments are made about the pedagogical conditions for the development of qualitative competence in students of preschool education. Also, the article contains some opinions about the issues of professional competence and its formation.

Keywords. competence, qualitative competence, educational process, method, knowledge, skill, activity, development, deficiency.

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ КВАЛИМЕТРИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ У ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Курбанова Мухтасархан Бахромовна

Магистрант университета Кокан

Абстрактный. В данной статье подробно комментируются педагогические условия развития качественной компетентности учащихся дошкольного образования. Также в статье содержатся некоторые мнения по вопросам профессиональной компетентности и ее формирования.

Ключевые слова. компетентность, качественная компетентность, образовательный процесс, метод, знание, умение, деятельность, развитие, недостаток.

INTRODUCTION

Pedagogical innovations and methods of quantitative assessment of the quality of pedagogical activity are being applied to the educational process in higher educational institutions of the world. In the "Incheon declaration" adopted at the International Education Forum held in South Korea until 2030, "improving the process and tools for evaluating the quality of education, implementing

mechanisms that allow to determine the achieved results"[4,25], worldwide Systematic work is being carried out to create equal conditions for the quality of education of learners, to introduce innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process, to implement large-scale practical projects to evaluate pedagogical parameters and characteristics of knowledge, pedagogical effects on the individual. In the world educational and scientific research institutions, scientific researches are being carried out on the assessment of the quality of education, the adaptation of pedagogical objects to their qualitative characteristics, the development of qualitative competencies of students, and the improvement of innovative pedagogical activities based on the qualitative approach.

Also, special attention is paid to scientific research on improving the effectiveness of qualitative competence development models, innovative methods and ensuring the success of the pedagogical content of e-learning resources based on the qualitative approach. In recent years, in our republic, raising the quality of education in higher education institutions, improving the educational system based on the organization of pedagogues' certification, creating new generations of educational content, normative bases for the development of educational resources of pedagogical qualimetry is being created. "Educating young people who are independent-thinking, have a firm outlook on life, are loyal to the Motherland, deepening democratic reforms and increasing their social activity in the process of civil society development"[1] were defined as priorities. As a result, opportunities for developing qualitative competence of students of higher education institutions have increased.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", February 7, 2017 "On further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan

on the strategy of development actions" No. PF-4947, dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" PF-5847- Decree No. PQ-2909 dated April 20, 2017 "On measures to further develop the higher education system", Decree No. PQ-2909 dated June 5, 2018 "Increasing the quality of education in higher education institutions and on additional measures to ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" No. PQ-3775, No. PQ-3151 of July 27, 2017 "Highly educated "On measures to further expand the participation of economic sectors and branches in improving the quality of training of specialists" and other regulatory legal documents related to this activity serve as the regulatory and legal basis of our research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The issues of developing qualitative competence of preschool education students have been reflected in a number of studies. In her research work, J.O. Tolipova focuses on the goals, tasks, scientific research methods, and actual problems of the pedagogical quality science. In addition, his research works provide information about the prospects and problems of using pedagogical qualitative methods in the educational process, and the problems of the science of testology. In the works of A.I. Subetto, I.N. Belozarov, N.A. Vasilyeva and others, the theoretical foundations of pedagogical qualimetry were considered, its problems were identified, the methodology of using expert evaluations in conducting pedagogical research was described, a comparative analysis of qualitative and other methods was carried out, research in pedagogy was carried out. Wide possibilities of expert methods are shown.

Before analyzing the qualitative competence, we will analyze the terms of competence and professional competence.

Competence - Latin means capable, capable. Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the

acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. In addition to professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, competence includes initiative, cooperation, ability to work in a group, ability to realistically evaluate, logical thinking, ability to sort and use information.

Professional competence - is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of professional activities by a specialist in a certain field and the ability to apply them in practice.

On the basis of the descriptions described above, it is possible to highlight the characteristics and qualities of professional competence: professional competence is manifested in a specialist operating in various fields; it is recognized as an integral quality that illuminates a personal, psychological characteristic; a specialist with this quality uses existing knowledge, skills, qualifications, and experience in various situations in order to effectively solve professional tasks and problems; serves to master new knowledge of the specialist field, self-development and improvement.

Qualimetric competence - establishes the fundamental importance of quality measurement and sets requirements for the content and methods of measurement and evaluation functions. First of all, it focuses on the evaluation of the conditions that help to develop the child's personality in all aspects.

Now we will analyze the history of the formation of qualitative competence. The historical-pedagogical analysis of the history of the problem made it possible to distinguish the following periods of its formation: the end of the 19th century - the mid-30s of the 20th century; mid-30s - 60s of XX century; 60s - 90s of XX century; From the mid-90s of the 20th century to the present time. Here's a look at each era:

Views on different periods of qualitative competence

Periods	Years	Tasks of periods
First period	The end of the 19th	The problem is characterized by the fact that it is not

	century, the middle of the 30s of the 20th century	a subject of special study, the terminological apparatus is not formed, it is not scientifically based. In pedagogical practice, there are rare cases of teachers organizing separate training for qualitative knowledge
Second period	30-60 years of XX century	In the 20th century, a systematic scientific study of specific aspects of the problem and their practical introduction to professional training began: active assessment of students and mathematical readiness
Third period	60-90 years of XX century	A comprehensive study of the problem was formed. At this time, issues of a comprehensive approach to the professional training of pedagogical personnel, the scientific bases and methods of pedagogical qualimetry, the theory of educational quality management were actively developed, as well as information technologies were developed in education, student assessment activities and forms and methods of teaching mathematics were improved.
The fourth period	From the mid-90s of the 20th century to the present	The problem of qualitative training has been comprehensively and comprehensively studied, it is characterized by the introduction of this type of training into the practice of professional education.

Based on the results of research on the development of qualitative competence of preschool education students, the qualitative competence of students was considered as the sum of knowledge, skills, skills and practical experience necessary for successful professional activity in one or another field. Also, we understand the essence of the concept of qualitative competence of preschool education students as a special type of professional-pedagogical training aimed at developing qualitative competence.

We determined the extent of knowledge, skills and abilities for the successful use of qualitative methods that allow drawing conclusions at the level of qualitative competence in pedagogical practice. When assessing the level of qualitative competence, it is necessary to take into account the availability and quality of pedagogical objects, processes and events during the educational process, pedagogical practice and qualification work, practical activity experiences on the use of qualitative methods. Pedagogical qualimetry is the structure of the teacher's pedagogical activity, depending on the multifaceted pedagogical process, and occupies the most important place in the fields of pedagogical sciences. It should be noted that the pedagogical quality determines the quality of the pedagogical process and the teacher's pedagogical activity.

Methodological problems of pedagogical quality measurement have not been sufficiently studied by scientific researchers and the problems in this field are waiting for their solution. The analysis of the literature shows that the methodological foundations of pedagogical qualimetry are directly related to the socio-economic development of society, the state and social orders placed on educational institutions, and the works carried out on its methodological foundations have been developed on the basis of the logical unity of the society's socio-economic development.

Even in the life education system, many managers prove the need to train them to objectively assess the changing qualities of a person's cognitive activity. Research shows that increasing the effectiveness of teaching and skill development is directly related to improving the quality of student achievement assessments. The use of modern technologies opens up additional opportunities in the system of evaluation of educational results as qualifications and skills. Among the evaluation methods, tests (tests), which include the organization of computer and remote testing, occupy an important place.

Two principles of knowledge control are used in educational systems:

- to evaluate the learner's actions and determine the level of knowledge based on the student's knowledge in the field of the subject and the rules for evaluating students' actions;

- control of standardized knowledge on a set of selected special tasks and the student's answers to them.

Computerized testing technology should have the following main features:

the presence of an interactive motor environment;

multi-subject application;

reflect the future model of the subject area at an appropriate level during the test process;

the possibility of choosing a test algorithm;

the possibility of adding (attachment, integration) to various educational technologies; the ability to create a profile;

the possibility of changing the size;

(to work, get, learn, implement) ease, availability;

user-friendly interface;

conduct (maintain) database of multi-level test tasks;

ability to control/adapt test planning and management;

designed to increase performance and motivation.

In recent times, instead of the traditional concept of "control", in addition to the concept of "diagnosis", the concept of "monitoring" has been used. Monitoring in the "educator-learner" system means a set of control and diagnosis activities that originate from the definition of the goals of the educational process and provide dynamic control of the learner's mastery levels.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Taking into account the above points, we put forward the following suggestions and recommendations:

1. It requires the development and implementation of methodological and technological instructions for solving qualitative issues in the development of the system implementation mechanism at various stages and forms of education.

2. It is necessary to develop the qualitative competence of students in inductive and deductive logical directions based on the division of modular teaching technologies into variable stages.

3. It is necessary to develop adaptive programs based on foreign experiences in the development of qualitative competence among students of higher education institutions.

CONCLUSION

Modern trends aimed at improving the quality of education place high demands on the state, society and scientific community to solve the problem of professional-pedagogical training of teachers and students of higher education institutions. In the conditions of the development of today's educational quality management systems, pedagogical staff should have a high level of qualitative competence, and this will help them to correctly implement the control of the educational process and improve the quality of education based on it. allows them to make management decisions. For this reason, studying the problem of qualitative competence within the professional training of students of higher educational institutions is of great interest.

The content of the development of qualitative competence of students of higher educational institutions was improved based on the step-by-step creation of an active-creative environment aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the use of modular teaching technologies and the leveling of variable stages of adaptive adaptation to the developmental educational trajectory.

Based on the results of the research on the development of qualitative competence of students of higher education institutions, the qualitative competence of students of higher education institutions was considered as a sum

of knowledge, skills, skills and practical experience necessary for successful professional activity in one or another field. .

Taking into account the uniqueness of the development of qualitative competence in students and modern organizational and pedagogical tools, the following set of conditions were distinguished: the use of the rating system of evaluation as a factor of involvement in the process of developing qualitative competence in students; to give a creative character to the preparation process by using educational projects; strengthening the practical orientation of qualitative training based on the use of the opportunities of the external information-educational environment.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
2. Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947.
- 4 Incheon declaration // Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (Word Education Forum, 19-22 may 2015. Incheon, Republic of Korea). – 48 p.
5. Nurdiddinov F.R. Development of qualitative competence in students of higher educational institutions. PhD. diss author. T.: 2023.
6. Занина Л.В., Меньшикова Н.Л. Основы педагогического мастерства /Учебное пособие для студ. пед. вузов. – Ростов-на-Дону, Феникс, 2003. – С.200

7. Usmonaliyev I.M. Improving the professional competence of future history teachers based on historical thinking. PhD. diss author. Kokan. 2023